

Climate and Health

Artur Victoria

Forewords

When we talk about NGOs that are climate pro activists or when an unknown person appears to impose on governments changes in economies and policies in the name of saving planet Earth, we usually simply give an unformed opinion of this news that the media explores.

I think that here, a slight analysis, although light we recognize the existence of the issue in the end of reading the Paper we are left with data to form an opinion and accept or not the proposal that we also make.

Environment

The current world view of the environment allows for a broader and more detailed coverage of what happens to the environment where all living things are.

Disasters, tragedies, plunder and exploitation of natural resources have been increasingly explicit in the face of human society, causing environmental imbalances and leading to the exhaustion of nature.

The purpose of sustainability is that human beings consider themselves integrated with nature, being able to develop their actions in balance with the environment in which they live.

In the evolutionary history of human thought, it is noted that the way of thinking of man has been changing throughout history, which clashes with the old Cartesian paradigm and with the new paradigm, that of sustainability.

Knowing the evolutionary process of human thinking can be pointed as causes for the diagnosed problem: environmental problems have not bothered people enough for them to act;

- There is no personal motivation or initiative to trigger environmental actions;
- Awareness does not necessarily trigger changes in attitudes;
- The non-accountability of people in the face of environmental issues.

Solutions to the problem come from existing programs and projects that work on environmental awareness, awareness and awareness, with an emphasis on causing

commotion to people so that they can be willing to make the changes needed to achieve sustainability.

ONG's and individual's seeking their own popularity on the media, try to promote protests about how the States have the legal and practical approach of issues to sustainability, however without pointing any solution.

The only solution for the future it is to build new cultural, social, political and economic values thus contributing to the formation of a new world consciousness for the benefit of life and all the diversity existing in nature.

Environment and Human Behaviour

Environmental action today is not yet in line with conscious population. We are stuck on concrete acts to minimize impacts we have caused.

Timid political movements and most are electoralists (seeking by votes) try to convince that people are collaborating with nature as a small part of the city's garbage is sorted for recycling, and when the rulers change the projects are neglected or abandoned, they start another environmental program as if be the first to worry about the environmental issue.

The search for the reasons that make conscious action the generator of attitudes and processes that can begin to mitigate environmental problems is significant given the inconsistency of conscious people and the lack of permanent environmental actions.

Working for a healthy environment, in the effective action of an organized society and concerned about knowing, understanding and exercising their responsibilities.

Referring to Educational Medicine, (KIKUCHI, 1991 p. 166) warns:

AUTOCURATERAPY cannot be compared with conventional medical therapeutic action. The goal of SELF-CURE THERAPY is to empower patients, which should be a fundamentally self-educational, non-medical act. The expropriation of health, detaining for doctors the exclusivity of the right to treat patients and the author's difficulty, using the current legislation, obeys, fundamentally, ignorance and financial interests. This is one of the main factors that cause disease in the troubled modern world. The disease is like a fire and the doctor is like the fireman.

Despite the full mobilization of the full capacity of the doctor (fire-fighter) and the use of all his equipment, there are still numerous serious diseases (large fires) that develop in parallel with the rapid evolution of today's mechanical science and technology. It is no use seeking only the technological and practical progress of the fire-fighter with his equipment and instruments, if we do not strengthen ourselves and prevent fire. We

must beware of the minor flames of individual disease as well as of the great fires (epidemics and wars).

Disease emerges as a possibility of growth, as an obstacle that contributes to our awakening awareness that imbalance is fundamental to maintaining relative balance.

So what you are looking for is not knowing how to put out the fire, because if you don't know, just study it and one has the most effective method for this. What you want is self-defence environment.

The expropriation of nature is bad, compared to Kikuchi's earlier reference to health. Treating the evil is not enough, it must be prevented and for this it is necessary to investigate what was lost and brings back the habits, returns to the balance for maintenance, and also seeks the natural balance of ecosystems.

Education plays a strategic role in the Environmental Management process, in the education of children and young people, incorporating human and environmental values, enhancing the meaning between everyday practices and the theory launched in the classroom, leading to a culture of sustainability, a culture harmonious coexistence between human beings and between them and nature.

The pursuit of sustainable development seems utopian, however, utopias are ideas for building something you dream of, and dreaming is generating hope.

It is to make abstract desire a palpable reality, to stop rambling to set foot on firm ground. Developing sustainability does not mean focusing solely on production, it is thinking and solving small proposals to indulge the natural logical process, that is, seeking in nature the answers to solve problems.

Problems were created by humans - we are part of the natural, the organic, and that depends on it.

We must go back to our origins to rethink the human way of life. Search for what has been lost to fit the missing piece to return to participate in the Earth's life cycle.

Sustainable development elects as its basic resource the creative initiative of people and the fundamental objective of their material and spiritual well-being. In well-functioning communities, even when there is poverty, there are also ingenious survival strategies.

The relationship between environment and development must cease to be conflicting to become a partnership relationship. The key to this is the need for peaceful coexistence between good environmental quality and economic development.

In order to take action to protect the environment, the mystery between consciousness and its ability to take conscious, committed and responsible actions to

propagate problem solutions and significant environmental improvements must be unravelled.

It is not only possible to plant trees in gardens each year in the environment week and to worship at this time as if it had a great effect on people and the environment.

Attitudes need to be planted in conscious people, it is not important to be environmentally conscious if there are no actions to mitigate environmental impacts.

The continuation of environmental underdevelopment is the continuation of throwing food scraps into the same brass as recyclable materials or while forests are being devastated daily, eliminating various endangered species of both flora and fauna, and the responsible authorities are not pressured to make this safeguard.

Understanding the underlying basis of action is of great importance in reaching conscious people so that they can have their attitudes consistent with their thinking.

Discovering the generating factor in actions gives you a much larger tool than just awareness. If awareness were sufficient, there would be no major concerns about the environmental issue, as it is evident in society the instituted existence in various segments of multipliers of environmental awareness.

Perhaps most do not see the seriousness that environmentalists have seen, hence the need for shock treatment, that is, to see the reality that shocks emotionally about being and doing with nature and the like.

If every environmentally conscious person who has no reason to act on the environmental issue is instigated at the right time to develop even individual attitudes aimed at remedying or preventing environmental damage, the work will be more than a contribution to environmental education, but yes, the trigger that triggers in each person their desire to make their current way of life different, for healthier attitudes from a particular point of view, emotional-psychological, actor in the great changes necessary for the preservation and conservation of an integrated world between human being and nature as they always were, one thing.

In order for the research have a direction, that points in only one direction, disentangling itself from the nuances that may intervene in its real objective, it is therefore necessary to infer the problem question:

- Why are many people, even though they are environmentally conscious, do not have rationally corresponding attitudes, taking ecologically correct actions?

The problem

It faces a widespread civilization crisis. The search for a new paradigm of coexistence of a relationship with Earth rekindling as a pact of society to respect and preserve all that exists and has life.

Trust has to be hoped for a solution again, and only from this mutation does it make sense to start thinking about possible alternatives.

The symptoms of this crisis are reflected in all directions:

- Children are used as a production force for the world market;
- Many countries suffer from poverty, disease and hunger;
- The exclusion industry is fortunate for retired and unemployed seniors;
- The contempt of the culture of solidarity is fuelled by the neoliberals exalted by the privatization of property;
- The lack of hope for the establishment of alienated and culturally uprooted societies that live on waiting for miraculous solutions;
- The loss of culture of sensitivity, kindness, overexposure to violence shown by the media without shame or scruple;
- The lack of political morality, the acceptance of corruption, the illicit enrichment of politicians, the lack of outrage and the action of revolt;
- Carelessness about biodiversity, billions of years of knowledge accumulated by evolution can disappear between our fingers;
- the lack of love for our earth, the neglect to safeguard its richness and natural beauty, contaminated soils, poisoned water, dense air of pollution, destruction of native forests with the entire home of the beings that inhabit them.

A principle of self-destruction grows and tends to dominate the human mind as if it seemed a normal way of thinking, capable of undermining the physical-chemical and ecological balance of the planet by devastating the biosphere, risking all sorts of planetary living.

Life is dated to a few million or billion years of evolutionary development, threatened by its most modern and ultimate creation. This one that in its lack of control does not identify its origins and is no longer recognized with the elements that formed it. (LOMBORG, 2001)

According to Sachs (2008), the world population tends to double its number until the end of the twentieth century; therefore, an equitable development of human society is essential to reduce social differences.

For those who benefit from the unequal sharing of resources on a planetary scale have to give up a portion of the ecological space they occupy to those who need it.

Over the years of depredation, environmental degradation and extraction of finite resources, in a developmental and economic advance at unequal speed accumulating wealth and causing climate change, threatening the planet's liability and the survival of the species with double speed societies , unequal, forming true apartheid societies In this view of Sachs it is observed:

a) The transition to socially equitable and nature-friendly development depends on the responses to the crisis of the institutions which, to varying degrees, affect the three groups of countries: the eastern, southern and northern, as well as the international system ;

(b) The future of developing countries will depend on their ability to find effective public and private sector configurations in order to regulate social-economic relations on the one hand and between the socio-economic and social spheres on the other nature;

c) For prosperity, the North appears as a model, but it is not feasible to extend to the entire planet, for the amount of resources that the consumer society demands and for the amount of debris it produces and dumps in nature, so its questioning becomes necessary for strategies transition to more durable development on a planetary scale;

d) Economic growth is necessary, but by no means sufficient to guarantee development, growth can sustain from real development or from underdeveloped phenomena, which leads us to qualitative criteria. One can think of the technique of extensive growth for intensive growth, that is, one must oppose the ideal of a civilization of being in the fair sharing of having;

e) Needs are material and immaterial, ethical, political, social, cultural and economic in nature; guaranteeing income, improving purchasing power, access to a parcel of arable land, or even a social distribution program;

f) Industrial civilization in the north and its replicas in the south are characterized by the enormous waste of land resources, which leads to the destruction of nature's capital. This waste, in a way, is a reserve for development; these resources saved through more rational management could finance social spending or investments, while enhancing renewable resources. In the meantime, science and techniques need to be refocused on development priorities, subject to the rules of ecological prudence, recent biotechnological progress.

Deep Ecology

The Deep Ecology proposed by the Norwegian philosopher Arne Naess in 1973 (HEEMANN, 1993) serves as a response to the dominant view on the use of natural resources.

Arne Naess is included in the tradition of ecological-philosophical thinking by Henry Thoreau, proposed in Walden, and by Aldo Leopold, in his Earth Ethics.

He called it Deep Ecology for clearly demonstrating its distinction from the dominant paradigm.

And that all the problems arising from this destruction are directly related to human development. On the one hand, the desire to assume a more comfortable life sharpening the innate obsolescence of the so-called "modern" man, in the wildness of his ambitions, the scientific unveiling that drunks him to the point of obscuring the various natural sacrifices dedicated to his discoveries and hides behind him. of its technologies.

It can be said that much is consumed by nature to create the fastest processors ever seen, or to make an agricultural machine that replaces the work of a thousand men.

Life on earth can exist without humans, but man cannot live without other lives to feed and exchange matter and energy. The relationship between man and the other terrestrial living beings betrays his great folly. By indulging his obsolescence, he eventually leads to the extinction of several living species or indirectly reaches the path to achieve his superfluous goals.

The disregard for which human beings have considered the other life forms on the planet demonstrates the lack of understanding of the tenuous line that maintains the natural balance, which also leads us to believe that the need to maintain this balance to perpetuate living conditions is unknown in the land.

Behaviour Paradigms

When man awakens to the new paradigm he moves from "the mechanistic conception of Descartes and Newton to a holistic and ecological view" (CAPRA, 2015), he leaves the anthropocentric values and seeks in the ecocentric values the vision of interdependence and makes it part of everyday life, a fundamental change in our thoughts, perceptions and values.

Further studies revert to the direction to clarify what a paradigm is. Thomas Kuhn in the Structure of Scientific Revolutions gives two meanings to the word paradigm.

The first, broader, has to do with “a whole constellation of opinions, values and methods, etc. members of a particular society”, founding a disciplined system whereby society orientates itself and organizes the whole of its relations. The second, stricter, derives from the first and means the reference examples, the concrete solutions of problems, considered and exemplary, and which replace the explicit rules in solving the other problems of moral science.

By contrast between the concepts, the first concept can be adopted as the one that most closely resembles the studies addressed in this work. The refusal to “downgrade the earth to a pool of natural resources or a physical-chemical reservoir of raw materials is that it is the basis for pursuing the new paradigm of feeling the need for new use of science and technique with nature, justifying the choice of the concept of paradigm.

From the mechanistic view created through the Scientific Revolution represented by Copernicus, Descartes, Bacon, Newton, Galileo describes the world as a machine driven by mathematical laws.

From the evolution of human thought, the revelation of chemical processes unravelling the functioning of living organisms has not yet been able to overturn the Cartesian paradigm.

Art, literature and philosophy were the initial triggers of true opposition to this dominant paradigm, with Lavoisier, William Blake, Goethe and Kant beginning to differentiate living beings as organisms capable of self-reproduction and self-organization, and see the integration between the parties and the Planet.

In earlier times the Greek and Roman references to the earth were affective, as Boff describes:

Everything was full of respect and veneration, for they saw things as mere inert beings, but full of irradiation and meaning. The earth, in the various expressions of the Great Mother, of cultivated land and home, was felt as a living organism. He cannot be violated or depredated.

Otherwise it avenges itself through storms, lightning, droughts, fires, earthquakes and volcanoes ... The human being maintained a relationship of veneration and fear towards Mother Earth.

This feeling has never been totally lost in humanity. There have always been spirits who are sensitive to magic and the enchantment of nature, even in modern times that has decrypted the world and reduced it to a chest of resources for technology to exploit.

Nowadays this feeling resurfaces from the so-called Earth sciences. They also tend to see Earth more and more as Gaia, a living, highly organized, subtly balanced super organism, always fragile and always undone, as the theory by NASA scientist Lovelock (1991) puts it.

Arising from the interactions between the parts, if dissected, into isolated elements, these properties are destroyed. Systemic thinking has revolutionized scientific thinking, aroused by the impact arising from the realization that systems cannot be understood by analyzing their parts, but broadly, contextually, as opposed to analytical thinking, that in order to understand something it is necessary to isolate - there.

The paradigm shift from mechanistic to systemic thinking leads us to reflect on materialistic philosophy, in which human beings came to believe in matter as the only consistent reality, the other phenomena are secondary derivations of it. For systemic thinking matter can be viewed in another way, as energy, matter is not simply material but stabilized energy, full of complex interactions. It further clarifies that matter, the philology of the word suggests, is the mother of all things, even of life which is the self-organization of matter.

The foundations for the creation of the dominant paradigms nowadays arose from the main philosophical currents started from the modern era (17th century) and the development of the sciences.

These generated models of development incompatible with the ecological balance in the process of civilization of the western world, which eventually triggered the present environmental crisis.

In turn led the contemporary society of the century XX, the formation of environmental thinking.

The historical antecedents of the main philosophical-scientific currents that influenced the formation of environmental thinking mean that they led to peculiar concepts, models and forms of reasoning, that is, different paradigms. Highlight the most relevant paradigms of the Modern Age to the present day, Contemporary Age of the 19th century. XX provides clarification for understanding this process.

The Cartesian Rationalist Paradigm

"Rationalism" or "Cartesian rationalism" is a philosophical current that emerged in the 17th century. XVII, formulated by the French philosopher Descartes (1596-1650).

This doctrine gives human reason the unique ability to know and establish the truth, regardless of the experience of the senses, rejecting any intervention of feelings and

emotions. Sensory experience for rationalists is a source of confusion and error about the reality of the world.

For Descartes, science is a deductive and demonstrative rational knowledge like mathematics. Deduction, or deductive argument, refers to a demonstration, which goes from general to particular, and which is capable of reaching a certain conclusion from a set of propositions that are linked to one another by following an order

Descartes' method consists of the decomposition of problems and thoughts into parts, these parts being organized by causal relations. Therefore, the whole is understood from the fragmentation and analysis of these isolated parts.

Descartes proves the truth of his statements by demonstrating the causal relations (or causal relations) that govern the object of investigation. Therefore, for Descartes, rationality is linear, that is, of cause and effect. He established that the one truth absolutely certain and certain, and completely without doubt, centered on his most famous phrase: "I think, therefore I am." It influenced Western science and culture.

In Cartesian philosophy the focus of intervention on nature is observed, which aimed to "know it in order to enjoy, control and dominate", using the power of human reason over nature.

Descartes stated that science must make human beings masters of nature and the world. Therefore, they have the power to dominate nature through scientific knowledge, being the "master possessors" of nature, not its .

It is also called mechanistic philosophy, which understands the world as if it were a machine, that is, the phenomena can be explained by mechanical devices. It argues that the universe is transparent from the look of reason and that everything can be explained through the particles of divisible matter. Nature is taken as the non-human world, stripped of all dynamism, all creativity, all sensitivity, all awareness, all sympathy or antipathy, all heat or coldness, all colour, taste and odours. ; in short, a totally mechanical world, without mystery, without life and without any fecundity

Cartesian rationalism influenced environmental thinking because it introduced a purely mechanistic conception of nature, for which it has no purpose, and is completely at the mercy of human exploitation. It stimulated the development of an instrumental rationality, using the means without any criteria to achieve the ends, leading to a disrespect and misuse and predatory of natural resources and ecosystems, as well as the development of polluting technologies.

Descartes' deductive reasoning, in which all phenomena are analyzed in their component parts, led to the fragmentation of thought and academic disciplines, leading to a reductionism in science. Hence the disciplinary division of classical science,

in which there is no connection between the disciplines and independence that are treated.

Thus there was also the conception that mind and spirit are separated from matter, that is, from the body, valuing mental work over manual work; appreciation of the isolated body of the mind; disregard of the psychological dimension of diseases, among others.

Consequently, man's departure from nature as if he were no longer part of it, the disappearance of the divine from the scientific view of the world, created a spiritual void that became characteristic of our Western culture.

The Empirical Paradigm

Empiricism is one of the great philosophical currents of the seventeenth to nineteenth centuries. In empiricism the explanation of knowledge and any phenomena can be obtained exclusively by observation and experimentation. They claim that reason, truth, and rational ideas are acquired by us through experience, as opposed to rationalists.

In this approach, scientific theory is the result of experimentation, so experimentation has the purpose of verifying concepts, confirming them, and producing them. It uses the inductive method, that is, part of making assumptions about the object to arrive at the definition of the facts.

Contrary to rationalism, empiricism states that our knowledge begins with the experience of the senses, that is, the sensations, which form perceptions (sight, hearing, touch, taste, smell). The association of repeated sensations produces the ideas. Experiences are perceived by sensory perception and habits and form ideas, in memory reason picks them up to form thoughts.

The Englishman Francis Bacon (1561-1626), was a classic empiricist, the first to develop the inductive method of scientific investigation, starting from particular data to arrive at a universal truth with deep passion for scientific experimentation, defending the valorisation of experimental research. Its motto was to know is power, within its conception that scientific knowledge is a practical instrument of reality control.

The empiricist doctrine was centred on practical science, based on the inductive experimental method, from which the laws were formulated, generalized from the observation of the repetition of phenomena with constant characteristics.

By this proposition that scientific knowledge serves to control reality, it opened the way for science to be used as an instrument of domination and control of nature.

Considering that it posited knowledge as dependent on personal experimentation, perceived by each person individually, it induced people to develop individualistic conceptions. Thus, the individual was more important than society. Specific groups with specific economic and exploitation interests that have negative effects on human actions in nature were seen only from the benefit side, and will result in greater economic gains for those specific groups.

Isaac Newton (1642-1727) used a methodology in which he combined rationality, empiricism, mechanism and determinism to develop his concepts. It drafted the Law of Gravity, greatly influenced biology, physics, chemistry, psychology and the social sciences since it was formulated, used as a basis for science in general, which occurred until the late 19th and early 20th centuries when it declined.

The limitations of the Newtonian model came only from the theory of relativity and quantum theory that created new forms of reasoning.

The Paradigm of Kantian Criticism

With the industrial revolution in the century in the eighteenth century, the advent of the steam engine established the link between science and technology, causing profound changes in the environment.

The optimism in the power of reason to reorganize the world, the Enlightenment, Century of Enlightenment or Illustration, gave rise to the criticism proposed by Immanuel Kant (1724-1804), through his work "Critique of Pure Reason".

Kantian criticism refers to the critical attitude, predominant stance at the time. A critical person is one who has definite and independent positions, thinks for himself and only accepts as truth what is established after his examination of the fact .

It is considered that from the Enlightenment men began to think for themselves, without being dominated and manipulated.

Criticism influenced environmental thinking by introducing the critical stance, as opposed to a stance of submissive acceptance of the facts. What made scientists and thinkers, especially from the 19th century. XX, began to question the dominant theories and scientific models, establishing a connection between them and the current environmental crisis. This stance allowed new paradigms to be created in order to solve the environmental disasters that have already occurred and to prevent others from occurring.

The Positivist Paradigm

Augusto Comte (1798-1857) was his main representative, based on positivism, emerged as post-Kantian philosophy in the nineteenth century, amid the transformations that occurred with the industrial revolution.

This doctrine created the “myth of scientism” by extolling science and the scientific method from which all possible and perfect knowledge came out. He believed in the benefits that science and technology would bring to the industrial revolution by providing capitalist progress.

Positivism denied the painful social consequences of industrialization, defended the legitimacy of industrial exploitation, and agreed with the existence of capitalist entrepreneurs and direct operators (the proletariat).

Positivism postulated that knowledge must be guided by a "systematic observation", a necessary condition for a sound scientific investigation, and that the human spirit must recognize the impossibility of obtaining absolute notions about its origin, the destiny of the universe, and to unravel the phenomena. What matters is knowing the phenomena through their laws, which makes science exist.

Positivism profoundly affected environmental thinking because it introduced the philosophy of progress, understood as technical-scientific advancement and accumulation of material goods, which was conquered with an unsustainable style of development, produced by a degrading dominion over nature.

Technology and science were instruments of man's domination of nature, from which he could lay down details about natural phenomena. Admitted the emergence of new scientific theses, because it considered the relative scientific knowledge and not absolute, this allowed new approaches and new environmental approaches.

The overvaluation of facts, evidence and experience was poignant, to the detriment of metaphysical or transcendent phenomena, that is, it neglected anything that transcends the limits of possible experience and any intervention of a principle superior to it, beyond our ability to know. .

The Vision of Contemporary Science

The Vienna Circle, which emerged in 1926, brought together a group of thinkers and scholars of science, led by Moritz Schlick (1882-1936), to discuss the problems of science, logic and scientific methodology. It is the neo-positivist tendency, also known as logical empiricism or logical positivism, in which some empiricist principles are taken up in the development of a theory and methodology with an emphasis on experimentation and verification in which knowledge is interpreted through statements or sentences. .

Critical rationalism, which argued that science, is rational, advocated by Karl R. Popper (1902-1994). He introduced into science the idea that "what proves that a theory is scientific is that it is fallible and accepts to be refuted," that is: it is not enough for a theory to be verifiable; it is precious eventually to prove that it is false. It is the condition of refutability, if the theory resists refutation will then be confirmed or corroborated.

Jurgen Habermas characterizes contemporary societies as rationalized societies, referring to instrumental reason, which preaches the use of means to achieve ends, aiming at the domination of nature for profit, placing science and technique at the service of capital. One way to denounce that our technological world is mainly driven by economic development.

Therefore, according to what we saw about the paradigms that dominated each space in time of the philosophical development of humanity, with their specificities creating lines of reasoning and unique perceptions that characterized them, giving their own identity, the proposition arises that the paradigm current runs through all the previous ones, having taken their foundations in parts of them all. Every conceptual basis of the dominant philosophical paradigm has had repercussions on the culture, environmental thinking, and developmental lifestyles of contemporary societies.

From these analyzes it is possible to understand the current paradigm, which has adopted thoughts, attitudes and actions of usurpation and degradation of the environment, leading also to social oppression, justifying the still prevailing condition of unfeasibility.

Economic Development and Environmental Awareness

Observing economic development and the environment, it can be said that globally, companies have begun to cooperate to minimize the negative effects of pollution and to demand environmental liability. International cooperative agreements and actions have been able to police and prosecute violators of reasonable emissions standards. There are possibilities of reconciling economic interests with environmental interests, but the prevailing economic thinking that guides most governments is that everything must be submitted to it and that ecology is the externality of the economy. Human business is only part of nature's business, so economics should be viewed as part of ecology.

The environmental issue should be considered one of the most important challenges that the business world will face in this first decade of the millennium. Enterprises should assume fundamental importance in this regard, acting promptly proactively and abandoning any reactive posture, as Callenbach (1993) advocates. Environmental

awareness in developed countries, where increased environmental awareness has provided the notion of the environment as a partner rather than as a restrictive factor for economic activities. This is what made awareness as if it had been imposed on development, which began to put profit adding to the environmental issue, increasing their incomes by adopting appropriate environmental policies. Companies that do not understand this new force relationship are bound to disappear, because the more citizens behave as consumers of political ideas and attitudes, the greater pressure will be placed on the crucial issue.

The increased concern for the environment is based on some assumptions, as shown in Figure 2.1 below, according to the order of priority mentioned by Callenbach (1993, p. 26).

From this awareness came the perception that it is necessary to increase profit, but now with the vision of well-being, without causing damage to the environment, sensitizing the consumer to the commotion of somehow improving the environmental situation. For radical protectionists, especially those in developing countries, the solution to growth was to accelerate rising incomes by adopting environmentally sound policies.

Hence the search for quality and much more now focused on the ecological responsibility side of the company, Environmental Quality.

Environmental quality consists of meeting physical, chemical, biological, social, economic and technological requirements that ensure the stability of environmental relations in the ecosystem in which the activities of the organization are inserted.

To transform the polluting environment and end the waste of production processes in industries already established as threats to the environment, the application of Quality Management techniques is a great result for these changes.

Total quality is the tool capable of taking care of the production process reducing the raw material used to produce generating a smaller amount of waste and waste. Assessing the industry's ability to respond to waste and effectively contribute to environmental improvement is environmental quality. By juxtaposition is then the Environmental Quality through the use of an instrument Environmental Management, which is defined as the set of well-defined and properly applied measures and procedures aimed at reducing and controlling the impacts a business has on the environment.

The Environmental Management action cycle must cover from the project design phase to the actual disposal of the waste generated by the project.

For Callenbach et. al. (1993, p. 36), Environmental Quality “consists in meeting physical, chemical, biological, social, economic and technological requirements that ensure the stability of environmental relations in the ecosystem in which the activities of the organization are inserted”.

Interpreting the authors can be considered as the reversal of pollution and waste to a new reality that allows the maximum yield of the finished product per unit of raw material used.

Speaking of Environmental Quality involves the conscious use of raw materials as well as the energy and inputs necessary for the process. The quest for successful environmental performance, eco-efficiency, brings us back to a well-known condition for sustainability: awareness.

Ethical principles are excellent avenues for a more sustainable human organization, as long as it was globally and locally practiced and there was strong global support for a paradigm shift, as well as political will and action based on well-informed public opinion.

It is understood that in the process of globalization, the concept of citizenship becomes a universal value and ecological ethics is a matter of love, care, and implied in this view the engine of consolidation of ethics are individuals.

Therefore, companies that do not walk the line will not be able to attract the best talent, a fundamental source to compete. Also, the more consumers are aware and firm in their demands on companies, the less room there will be for unethical postures in the corporate world.

Companies have a relevant role in contributing to social consensus, through a sustainable business practice, which means changing values and orientation in their operating system, envisaging the preservation of the environment.

In this way the conscious consumer seeks to value the environmentally friendly products or those that have a link with the natural, which makes more entrepreneurs seek to adjust their product to the customer's wishes, leaving the non-renewable for a frantic search for sustainable alternatives. .

With agreed legislation and poor supervision, it has nevertheless produced effects, making a more significant advance to reduce pollution in the industrial sector, while its liquid and solid waste that pollutes the waters is added to that of the state urban sewage and agricultural activities, the sectors of which have not yet manifested themselves significantly, as the initiative by the government is starting with irrelevant campaigns in the face of the urgent need.

The concern of companies with environmental issues, although limited and insufficient, is of fundamental importance, however, if it is very far from ideal as the issue does not stand as isolated, but necessarily connected with social and cultural issues, is what It identifies with Capra (1982, p. 49): “the worldview and value systems that underlie our culture, [...]”.

The search for adaptation of production to environmental certifications shows how much companies care about the environment, but behind them is the exploration of a new growing market, that of environmentalists.

Despite this it is already a gain as to the need for change through action across all productive sectors.

For this author, it is understood that the certifications are at the crossroads of ambiguity and, in this sense, contradictorily demonstrate both dimensions: it is a concern more significantly for some, and it is a fad for others. Since no social forces can envisage implementing the environmental revolution, a small step is always better than nothing.

Therefore, as limited as the effects of certifications may be, environmental issues are becoming present in this sector which seeks the required quality and no longer stands in the same way as in the previous period.

Others authors states that the critical factor is a change in management philosophy and even a change in competitive strength. It is in the business interest to do well in any situation, so it is necessary to adapt to the situation the market demands.

Certifications represent an environmental concern especially for those sectors that seek to adapt the measures provided for in existing legislation. However, for many enterprises, environmental certification appears as another marketing mechanism, adapting to new times and the pressure of environmental activists.

While this aside the certifications other forms of environmental pollution remain intact. “The environmental tax is in this dilemma, corrects part of the environmental implications, but cannot yet embrace the horizon of the ecosystem in its complexity.

Capitalist production is by its very nature anti-environmental, including the progressive degradation or depletion of natural resources. Not to mention that in some sectors there is still no alternative to proceed in an environmentally sound manner, such as fossil energy derivatives (oil and coal). The rationality of the system in the short and long term implies the domination and destruction of natural resources, revealing the bias of unsustainable, once all nature is understood as natural goods for the purpose of private appropriation.

This requires more than awareness, it is necessary to break the lack of human sensibility, to understand and realize that human dignity is in all the conditions that society lives and overlap the reason of turning everything into consumable products for profit. .

From the considerations presented above, it can be assumed that there are two "different times" between the planet and its available resources, and the unbridled pursuit of development, from which it is transcribed:

While one of the times, the planet and its resources, is noticeable through a global analysis (many environmental situation reports have been released in recent years, with high credibility and representativeness of the authors), the other time, the entrepreneurial view, and is still undeveloped and poorly studied.

Therein lays the cause of the causes. The main cause of the perception crisis is the difference between the times of the actors involved in the process of global development, ie the entire population of the planet.

Sustainable development

In the official literature there is a set of concepts or meanings that often contradict each other. There are references to development, Sustainable Development, sustainability and support capacity, among others.

As Sustainable is an adjective that qualifies the noun Development it is not quantifiable, it can be assumed that each one has the right to issue his own concept or adapt it according to his needs or interests. The concept proposed by the UN, its specific forums, and later the Rio de Janeiro Conference (Rio-92), is considered one of the concepts, but not the only one.

The World Commission on Environment and Development, created in 1983, emphasizes that "Sustainable Development is one that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs", which can be highlighted as a logical concept meeting the needs of the world's poor in priority; and the perspective that the environment prevails in the face of advancing technology and social development.

The conception of Sustainable Development is for environmentalists it is an old aspiration of yours and requires the determination of new priorities by society, a new ethic of human behaviour and a recovery of the primacy of social, collective interests."

Today it can be seen that the environmentalists' position is being seen as a change in the production and consumption processes to reverse the environmental degradation and social misery caused.

This conception of environmental degradation would be misrepresented to the extent that it is interpreted by different social actors and is now perceived as a gateway into the country of international mechanisms for controlling our natural heritage at the time as a strategy for expanding the market and the environment profit.

There are, therefore, different conceptions for the concept in question and may present different meanings, such as the WWF (World Wild Foundation) that emphasizes its conservationist proposal, stating that an ecologically sustainable society is one that:

- (a) Conserve biodiversity and life support systems;
- (b) Ensure that the use of renewable resources is sustainable and that degradation non-renewable resources is minimized;
- c) Seeks to remain within the carrying capacity of ecosystems.

Among all these conceptions and those not mentioned in this work, the majority tends to focus on the defence of biodiversity, while initiatives regarding environmental rationality and the limit of carrying capacity are timid in their execution and even in their proposals.

In 1972 the Club of Rome entitled "Limits to Growth" was concerned with analyzing how to retain development and its destruction to the environment.

The issue is not to prevent, but to change the type of development as there is no development in itself, but a society that chooses the development it wants and needs.

One should talk about sustainable society or a sustainable planet as indispensable preconditions for truly integral development.

If society is sustainable, by definition, a sustainable society is said to achieve its needs without compromising natural capital and without prejudice to the right of future generations to meet their needs and to inherit a planet healthy with their preserved ecosystems.

A sustainable society should produce enough for itself and for the beings of the ecosystems where it is located; taking from nature only what it can replace, and that in practice society must be able to take on new habits and design a kind of development that cultivates care for ecological balances and functions within the limits imposed by nature.

Obsolescence needs to be contained, not necessarily to prevent consumption, but for consumption to be responsible.

Therefore, the triggering action of this type of development cannot be found in the various social segments, the market, the state, entrepreneurs, but in the person, the individual citizen, the community and other living beings who share the adventure of life. .

The International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN), the World Wildlife Fund (WWF) and the United Nations Environment Program (UNEP), in 1980, launched the first concept on Sustainable Development, by definition: [...] To be sustainable, development must take into account social and ecological as well as economic factors; the bases of living and nonliving resources; the advantages of long-term and short-term alternative actions .

The World Commission on Environment and Development, an entity created by the United Nations to carry out a study on the environmental situation and the priorities to be established at the 1992 Rio Conference, propagated the concept of sustainable development to conduct a study on the environmental situation and priorities to be set at the Rio Conference in 1992. For the World Commission on Environment and Development (1987) "sustainable development is one that meets the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs" .

For the United Nations Environmental Program (UNEP) originated after the Stockholm Conference, promoted by United Nations Organizations (UN) with the purpose of raising environmental awareness and action at all levels of world society, promoting care for the environment.

In 1993, the UN Human Rights Commission in its Declaration on the Right of Peoples to Development reports:

Development is a comprehensive economic, social, cultural and political process that seeks to constantly improve the well-being of the entire population and each person on the basis of their active, free and meaningful participation and the fair distribution of their benefits.

More practically, it can be said that social development aims to improve the quality of human life as human, including healthy and long life, education, political participation, participatory and not just representative social democracy, guaranteeing respect for human rights and protection against violence, conditions for proper symbolic and spiritual expression. These transformations lead to the transposition of various barriers such as coexistence between differences, cordiality in social relations, compassion for others in miserable or marginalized situations, the creation of compensatory measures and social inclusion.

The World Wildlife Fund (WWF) and the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) have devised a strategy for the future of life that lays out nine principles of Earth sustainability in *Caring for the Earth. The earth 1991*):

- a) Build a sustainable society;
- b) Respect and care for the community of living beings;
- c) Improve the quality of human life;
- d) Preserve the vitality and diversity of Planet Earth;
- e) Remain within the carrying capacity of planet Earth;
- f) Modify personal attitudes and practices;
- g) Allow communities to take care of their own environment;
- h) Generate a national framework for integrating development and conservation;
- i) Form a global alliance.

The expression sustainability in the approach of Sachs (1993), advocates the existence of five faces of sustainability: social, economic, ecological, spatial and cultural. These should be considered especially when planning development.

Social sustainability (SACHS, 1993 p. 14-18) is understood as the creation of a development process sustained by the vision of a just society and a civilization with greater equity in the distribution of income and goods, reducing the gap between living standards of the rich and the poor.

It can be added to this proposition of Sachs in juxtaposition to the theme of this paper, that social sustainability is directly dependent on the existence of consciousness focused on ethics and social equity on the part of this society.

Economic sustainability, for Sachs (1993) must be made possible through more efficient allocation and management of resources and a constant flow of public and private investments. It can be added in the author's view of this work the existence of respect for the economic needs of governments and entrepreneurs as a premise for this face of sustainability.

Ecological sustainability points to the need to increase the capacity of Earth's resources through:

- Creativity and the use of technology;
- limit consumption of fossil fuels, renewable and non-renewable resources;

- Reduce waste and pollution by conserving energy, resources and the 3R policy;
- To promote self-limitation in the consumption of materials by rich and poor countries; and
- To intensify research into low-waste, resource-efficient technologies for urban, rural and industrial development;

It also sets standards for appropriate environmental protection. The formation of environmental awareness focuses on this sustainability proposal as a precursor to triggering actions to meet the care of the environment.

Spatial sustainability (SACHS) is contemplated by:

- reducing excessive concentration in metropolitan areas;
- curb the destruction of fragile ecosystems; promote agriculture and forest exploitation through modern, regenerative techniques by small farmers;
- explore the potential of decentralized industrialization coupled with the new generation of clean technologies; and
- create a network of biosphere and nature reserves to protect biodiversity.

Considering the environmental awareness addressed in this paper for Sachs's proposal, it would be to conceive of the human being in his actions as an inherent part of the environment and that any intervention made in it must be cautious as to its subtraction or destruction and preparation for natural restitution so that it does not come affect them.

The cultural sustainability of Sachs (1993) should include in development processes the search for endogenous roots of modernization processes and integrated agricultural systems, processes that seek changes within cultural continuity and translate the normative concept of eco-development into a set of solutions specific to location, ecosystem and area.

In relation to environmental awareness, it would be to pursue sustainable development, which for a conscious view, would be learning to grow with the premise of caring for the living environment.

Any development would be valid only when it was firstly concerned with all the interventions and causal consequences to the environment before moving on.

Temporal sustainability can be conceived by the parallel that consciousness can be maintained over time by prevailing all other aspects of sustainability as long as none of

them is transgressed in essence under penalty of imbalance leading to collapse since they must always be in interdependence.

Alternatives for Sustainable Development

Among the relevant aspects that can set a new level in the relationship between humanity and nature are those defined as clean technologies; and since these are in our daily lives, their identification becomes more visible.

Clean technologies will protect the environment, are less polluting, use all resources more sustainably, recycle their products and waste more. They prevent pollution by generating little or no waste. If pollution is generated, clean technologies rely on other technologies for their treatment Brazilian Institute of Sustainable Production (IBPS).

The clean technologies proposal aims to improve the conditions and processes for information, access to and transfer of technologies, in particular to developing countries (UNCTAD, 2001).

According to Sachs (1986), "modern technology should be used for the development of new products (and markets) capable of adding value to agricultural, forestry and aquatic biomass, considering the occupational potential linked to its production and management renewable natural resources".

For the implementation of technological innovations it is necessary to consider the attitudes, beliefs and values of the "social actors", as technological transformations influence their mindset and their behaviour. Because if social groups are not prepared to accept and / or assimilate the impacts and consequences of technological transformations, surely the transformations will not be successful in generating their results, both in terms of productivity increase and in terms of development that may come about be sustainable.

For clean technologies Agenda 21 brings propositions such as:

a) Clean technologies suggest different patterns of social relationship. Its proposal is based on cohesive, solidarity community organizations based on strong motivations, values and common interests, so that each community can participate actively in building their own ways;

(b) Assuming technological innovation as a means of ensuring a socio-economic balance within contemporary society, then it can be considered as a necessary condition for the continuity and "sustainability" of the development process;

c) If technological innovations do not follow specific policy measures to avoid destructive practices, they will have similar consequences to unsustainable growth strategies, that is, the richer classes get these innovations introduced, while the poorer layers become even more impoverished.

The foundations of Clean Production are centred on five basic principles:

a) Precautionary principle - adopted in Europe, seeks precaution against workers 'and consumers' diseases and irreparable damage to the planet. It is the producer who must assume responsibility and the burden of proof that a particular product, process or material will not cause harm to man and the environment; b) prevention principle - proposes to replace end-of-pipe pollution control by preventing waste generation and consequent environmental impacts. Recommends process and product analysis and end-of-life consumption, disposal, disposal and treatment of waste, packaging and products.

Its objectives are:

- eliminate or reduce the generation of potentially polluting emissions;
- create measures for reorientation of design (project design) to products;
- reorient consumer demand and stimulate changing patterns of use or consumption of materials.

c) Principle of integration - covers two topics: the application of prevention and precautionary features in all production system flows and the product's Life Cycle Assessment. LCA was born in the 1970s and gained momentum in the 1990s to ensure the safety of products and processes for the environment and human health.

d) Principle of democratic control: the participation of employees, residents in the vicinity of the industrial plant, consumers and other segments of society, subject to the effects of products and processes of production of goods and services, is what delimit the survival strategies for Clean Production. ;

e) Public right of access to information: this right unfolds as follows:

- Citizens' right to know and have access to information about their environmental and natural resource conditions;
- The right to be consulted and to participate in decision-making affecting the environment;
- Rights of remedies and compensation for damage to the environment and human health.

Democratic participation is beyond the elaboration of these guiding principles of the actions of the capitalist world of production.

It is clear that workers and consumers are contributing to the technological innovations that are environmentally and socially responsible, as they are more aware that they are actors in changes in the degradation of nature also because they feel they are the victims of the environmental impacts of development and technology.

The relationship between humanity and nature currently projecting a sustainable future is directed towards the development of clean technologies.

Referring to Agenda 21 they are called “Environmentally Healthy Technologies”, as they protect the environment by reducing pollutant emissions, make use of resources in a sustainable manner, their products and waste are disposed of for recycling.

For Sachs (1993), new products should be developed by modern technology aimed at adding value to agricultural, forest and aquatic biomass, linked to the use of raw materials from renewable natural resources.

The rationalization of energy use, such as the use of steam, electricity, natural gas, etc., replacing fossil fuels at the power plant has a major effect on reducing the generation of gases and solid particles.

It is revealed in the details for the sustainability proposal that it is essential the existence of a different paradigm from the current one in the institutions that idealize it. In order for there to be a true search for sustainable development, the sustainability propositions described above reveal in their intentions the need for the individuals involved in this process to be aware of the interrelationship of each item in the process.

Thus, awareness is a precursor to any attempt to pursue sustainable development, which calls for the preparation of a true purpose in the action of the people involved, thus achieving the success of the process.

Zero emission

Launched by the United Nations University in 1994 as part of the Institute for Advanced Studies' Eco-Restructuring Program for Sustainable Development, the Zero Emissions Research Initiative (ZERI) has been linked to that university .

ZERI emerged at UNU as a result of the convergence of three currents of thought that have dominated the world scene in the last 60 years: development, focused on economic growth and the expansion of industrial production; social, attentive to individual and collective human well-being, and ecological, defending natural systems and the quality of the environment.

The Stockholm Conference and consecrated at Rio-92, consolidated ZERI by crystallizing the ideals of sustainable development proclaimed at these meetings as well as the search for appropriate strategies to promote it.

ZERI proclaims a paradigm shift in all economic activities, in particular industrial production processes. It integrates total quality principles and strategies with environmental quality requirements as a basis for promoting a new type of sustainable development.

From the first moment, ZERI acquired the distinctive mark of a visionary and innovative proposal, but embodied with business pragmatism. Its concept is still evolving and its applicability for sustainable development management has been demonstrated through examples of companies that adopt the strategies it proposes .

Using the knowledge of the principles of biological cycles, which above all consider all life existing on the planet, the ZERI concept seeks the harmonization of economic activities from this knowledge, generating material progress and quality of life, providing present generations what they need without compromising the possibilities that future generations also have.

The company survives from the stability of life-sustaining systems, as the ZERI concept considers that ecological and social sustainability are closely linked, and action strategies are primarily aimed at changing the paradigm of industrial activity, as in much of it is the cause of environmental degradation.

It applies as much to a company as to its entirety. As part of its larger strategy, ZERI promotes a five-step business change method. They apply, with appropriate adaptations, to the public sector, as well as to the regional administration and development of cities or islands, as is happening in some countries in Asia and Europe (more specifically Gotland / Sweden and Yakushima / Japan).

In the ZERI proposition industrial or business development should take as an example what demonstrates the dynamic processes of nature, so it is necessary to review current processes and technologies.

Waste is transformed into a source of energy, raw material has a greater use from extraction to benefit, which is a hindrance to production should be a condition for new proposals less aggressive or lucrative alternatives with a new way of thinking about the problem.

Thus, solving environmental, business, industrial and even social problems.

The evolution of total quality can be interpreted by the implementation of ZERI, with the full use of raw material, zero waste. This quality reflects promising changes in the

pursuit of continuous, inclusive improvement of environmental issues, enabling job creation and poverty reduction.

The premise for the implementation of ZERI is the change of paradigms, the perception of how to deal with complex problems.

The road ahead now requires taking into account economic growth, environmental quality and social development, which boil down to the concept of sustainable development.

As with clean technologies, Zero Emission also has as its prerogative the paradigm shift where it is intended to be deployed. Being perceptive to diagnose environmental problems and come up with solutions is environmentally conscious.

This once again affects people who must be prepared for the common, in this case, to look for alternatives to any kind of waste that may be degrading to the environment, since the usual elimination of carelessly impacting emissions is usual.

Therefore, the Zero Emission sustainability process also depends on awareness and determination in mobilizing in environmentally sound attitudes.

Eco-efficiency

To characterize this sustainability proposal is the report of the World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD) a coalition of 150 international companies that share a commitment to environmental protection, social equity and economic growth, or that is, sustainable development. According to this report one can conceive as understanding about eco-efficiency:

Eco-efficiency is a business management philosophy that seeks to encourage business economic growth while pursuing environmental improvements.

The search for business opportunities that will allow more environmental responsibility with more profit.

It proposes innovation and therefore growth and competitiveness. The WBCSD (2001) expresses its definition:

Eco-efficiency is achieved through the provision of competitively priced goods and services which, on the one hand, meet human needs and contribute to the quality of life and, on the other, progressively reduce the ecological impact and the intensity of use life-cycle resources to a level that at least respects the estimated carrying capacity of planet Earth.

Briefly it is said to create more value with less impact.

Eco-efficiency is not simply about fostering efficiency improvements in existing habits and practices, but rather looking for creativity and innovation in the search for new ways of acting.

Nor is it confined to areas intrinsic to business, but should involve supply and purchasing value chains, product managers, marketing specialists, and even the finance and management control departments.

The efficiency of this process must be achieved by integrating the three pillars of sustainability, the economy, ecology and social progress. However, care must be taken so that companies do not end up meeting only the first two pillars, leaving social responsibility to be charged later to those who are interested. Hence, the true sense of eco-efficiency for sustainability is emphasized, that companies to be rewarded with profit must therefore be concerned with improving the quality of life.

According to the WBCSD (2001) eco-efficiency is centred on three objectives:

- a) Reduction of resource consumption: includes minimizing energy use, materials, water and soil, favouring the recyclability and durability of the product, closing the materials cycle.
- b) Reduction of impact on nature: includes the minimization of gaseous emissions, liquid discharges, waste disposal and the dispersion of toxic substances, as well as boosting sustainable use of renewable resources.
- c) Improving the value of the product or service: this means providing more benefits to customers through product functionality, flexibility and modularity, providing additional services and focusing on selling needs customers actually need, which raises the possibility that customer receives the same functional need with fewer materials and less resource utilization.

Many companies still pursue a fourth objective, the implementation of an Environmental Management System (EMS) or Sustainability, integrated into the business management system, in order to boost the eco-efficiency approach.

The EMS is a way of ensuring that all sustainability-related risks and opportunities are correctly identified and efficiently managed, e.g. looking for opportunities that can be found in the following four areas:

- a) Re-engineering its processes to reduce energy consumption resources and pollution and avoid risks while saving costs; (
- b) Creatively revaluing its by-products in cooperation with other companies;
- c) Redesign their products to meet customer needs;

d) Rethink other markets and completely reshape demand and supply.

Eco-efficiency opportunities are not limited to large and international companies. Small and medium enterprises and micro businesses can also benefit from eco-efficient solutions. Similarly, service companies can use the concept in the way they provide their services and thus help customers become more eco-efficient as well.

Through the work of the OECD, the US President's Council for Sustainable Development (PCSD), the European Commission and other government institutions, eco-efficiency has been adapted as a concept for policy macro-economic level for industrialized countries as well as developing, emerging and transition economies.

Improving eco-efficiency does not automatically lead to sustainability.

Simply improving in relative terms (value for impact) can also mean a general increase in the impact of activities and create unacceptable damage or irreversible damage. The European Environmental Agency states that “absolute reductions in nature use and associated environmental pressures may be necessary to stay within the carrying capacity of planet Earth so that separation, in absolute and relative terms, between the growth of welfare and the use of nature”.

The business world cannot achieve eco-efficiency alone, progress requires going beyond the internal actions of each company; requires close cooperation between the various stakeholders.

It needs society to create a facilitating system that will enable companies and markets as a whole to become more eco-efficient. This denotes the premise that culture in society must be transformed according to the objectives of eco-efficiency.

Governments play a very important role in creating these conditions.

- They can implement a policy that fosters economic growth and favours the reduction of resource use and avoids pollution, with incentives for eco-innovation.

- They can use various incentives to promote action for progress and support initiatives for advancing eco-efficiency - rewarding leading companies and pushing for the latest ones.

- Incentives to reward eco-efficiency will drive innovation in the right direction and create new products and services.

Eco-efficiency creates more value with fewer resources through new product and service designs and innovative solutions.

The most successful companies will be those that set the most difficult environmental objectives and meet them through new technologies and practices (WBCSD, 2001).

The European Environmental Agency states that “absolute reductions in nature use and associated environmental pressures may be necessary to stay within the carrying capacity of planet Earth so that separation, in absolute and relative terms, between the growth of welfare and the use of nature”.

For the existence of the sustainability proposal through eco-efficiency it is also necessary to take as a precept the transformation in the way of thinking in the business, consumer society and government caste, as mentioned authors.

From the new form of thinking that must consider all the elements that participate directly or indirectly in the activities that lead to development, that is, the paradigm shift and Capra's systemic model (1982; 1996).

It is observable in the instances to seek sustainable development the preparation of those involved to have environmental awareness, and from the perception of environmental elements can develop attitudes that can continue giving balance to the system.

Environmental Perception and Social Mobilization

Our perception of the world that makes us interact with the environment is the sensations perceived through the sensory organs. The ability to see, hear, smell, touch and taste provides an interpretation of everything around you.

There are two exponential movements about sensation and perception until the twentieth one century: the empiricist conception and the intellectualist conception. Empiricists regard sensations as physical-physiological responses to external stimuli acting punctually on our sense organs, nervous system, and brain. Sensations are independent, perception commands them.

Perception and sensation are passive agents in the face of the outer field's activities on our body.

For intellectualists, sensation and perception are phenomena that are directly related to the intellectual capacity of the subject of knowledge. In this case, the subject is active in the face of events external to him.

The sensation is only processed and led to a perception when there is an activity of understanding what one feels, when one senses the thoughts rationally.

Safeguarding the differences, both the empiricists and the intellectualists believed in the cause and effect relationship as a mediator between external things and the subject.

Sums of sensations, organized into perceptions, synthesize the perceived object.

The world is not what I think, but what I live for; I am open to the world, I undoubtedly communicate with it, but I do not own it, it is inexhaustible.

Perception is an experience endowed with meaning. It can be said that in the global perceptions of an object or format, the real is described in the act of meaning and significance.

A message that is dictated by thought and perception conditioning a relationship, a communication between what is perceived and the perceiver.

Reality reveals itself not only with the measurements made on it, but also through the intermediation and analysis of the subjective changes that compose it and permeate the integrative relationship of the subject in the world and the world in the subject.

A phenomenological philosophy is still “an exact science, but it is also an account of space, time, the lived world it is necessary to rediscover the experience behind the thought, to dive into the sensible and to find the invisible behind the visible, since one is the existential condition of the other

Visible woven invisibility: depth is not the third dimension of space, it is the invisible of visibility, that without which we do not see and without which nothing would be visible; the faces of the cube we do not see sound the invisible of the cube, that which makes it a visible thing.

The invisible is not a positive negative that would duplicate the positivity of the visible, but what the visible is visible to, its inside and out, one of its dimensions, an absence that counts in the world.

We perceive and define our way of relating to things and others positively or negatively, perceive things as instruments or as values, react positively or negatively to colours, odours, tastes, textures, distances, sizes

So it can be said that one is in the world as active subjects, imparting new meanings, values and interpretations to perceived things, since they are part of our lives and interacting with the qualitatively, meaningfully and structurally perceived world.

The complexity of these relationships that are established between our senses and the world, between our bodies and the bodies of others and / or things, between the outside and the inside, that we should talk about in a perceptual field of intersected spheres of reason, emotion, thought, imaginary (meaning, interpretation), individualization, socialization, sensation and learning .

It is from the subjective encounter between things and the subjects that the perceptual act reveals what was not known as the visible component of concepts, giving meaning, or making them meaningful.

Addressing aspects of the urban environment, the psychological and topological spaces are distinguished. The first reveals behavioural aspects arising from the use of urban spaces, while the second concerns the perception of the physical formations of the city. The study, inserted in the UNESCO program Man and Biosphere (MAB), was interested in residents' expectations regarding the recovery and accessibility of river use, as well as its importance in the construction of the city's imagination.

One of the most common manifestations of population dissatisfaction is vandalism. Aggressive conduct on physical and architectural elements, usually public, or located near public places.

This is mostly the case among the poorer social classes, who are subjected to poor quality of life every day, from the problem of urban transport to the quality of the neighbourhoods and housing estates, hospitals and schools on which they depend, etc.

To understand a person's environmental preference, we would need to examine their biological heritage, upbringing, education, work, and physical surroundings. At the level of group attitudes and preferences, it is necessary to know the cultural history and experience of a group in the context of the physical environment. In neither case is it possible to clearly distinguish between cultural factors and the role of the physical environment. The concepts "culture" and "environment" overlap in the same way as the concepts "man" and "nature" (TUAN 1980, p. 67).

Manifestations are presentable when the referential is subjective, when the approach is, for example, an interview with a resident of the countryside where the environment perceived by him is loaded with affective values is his daily life and is consistent with his familiarity (lived landscape).

For environmental technicians and researchers, the representations are of conceptual orders and committed to the scientific objectivity (landscape not lived).

For Piaget perception consists of functional exchanges between the individual and the external environment, which have two aspects: cognitive and affective.

That is, while the individual knows the outside world, he develops feelings about it, the most important aspect being the cognitive, while the affective is considered as the energy of the system.

Affectivity is the impulse that directs perception, that is, the emotion of linking people to their space.

Each image and idea about the world is then composed of personal experience, learning, imagination, memory and value systems.

The places we live, the ones we visit and tour, the worlds we read and see in artwork, and the realms of imagination and every fantasy contribute to our images of nature and man.

Research on environmental perception is situated in a typical aspect of relations and interactions between man and the environment, because it is an approximation where the understanding of the environment, individual or collective, is considered as one of the determining factors that characterize that environment through choices and behaviours. It is possible to investigate what people's perception of their environment is; how culture and experience affect this perception; what are the attitudes towards the environment; and what is the role that environmental perception plays in the spatial arrangement of the environment and in the appearance of landscapes.

Investigations in major European and North American metropolitan centers have found that an increase in knowledge about the ecological crisis and the wounds of the earth does not necessarily lead to a change in attitudes and more respect and reverence for it.

What is essential is not knowledge, they say, but feeling. The more a person suffers from the degradation of the environment, becomes angry with the suffering of animals and revolts against the destruction of the earth's green spot, the more he develops attitudes of compassion and tenderness, protection of nature and a cosmic spirituality.

The study of mental processes related to environmental perception is fundamental to better understand the interrelationships of the human being with the environment, either individually or communally, in their expectations, judgments and conduct. The individual or group sees, interprets and acts in relation to the environment according to interests, needs and desires, receiving influences mainly from previously acquired knowledge, values, group norms, in short, from a set of elements that make up their cultural heritage.

The Sachs document pointed to the need to establish local Civil Development Forums - or Councils - for understanding, discussing, planning and executing Agenda 21.

Sachs (1996) suggests as strategies to narrow the gap between rich and poor that should be addressed in practice by the "ecological dimension providing viable means of existence, with institutional implications, encouraging respect for the environment and long-term vision for conservation of resources ". Thus enabling the natural potential to be exploited with due respect for ecological principles, meeting social needs and satisfying economic efficiency.

Sachs (1996) also mentions that “the evolution of mentalities” and the “fundamental notion of balanced development in harmony with nature” should be a guide for action in decision making.

Knowing how people act and why they act in this way, coupled with surveying the community organization, networks of influence and the intensity and form of community participation of their organizations, enables us to determine where and how to act to promote participation and co-operation - responsibility of all those involved in better soil management.

Perception involves the selection, identification and coding of relevant information within a remembered context of past information. Group and society attitudes are in accordance with what culture accepts as the true message, that is, it is in accordance with the images of society. The area of research concerning environmental perception in the relationship between man and the biosphere can be summarized as 5 objectives:

- a) Contribute to a more rational use of biosphere resources harmonizing local (inland) knowledge and those available in the exterior;
- b) Increase in all areas the rational understanding perceptions of the environment;
- c) Encourage local participation in development and planning with a view to a more effective accomplishment of a more appropriate transformation;
- d) To help preserve or record the perceptions and knowledge systems of the environment, which is fast disappearing in many rural areas; e) act as an educational instrument and agent of evolution and look for occasions to train research-related people.

Perception and Environmental Education

The aspirations of a community or population should be addressed in the environmental planning to which it will be subjected, as this aims to solve the alarming problems in the diagnosis that characterizes it.

These characteristics demonstrate the knowledge of the environment by people who live in it and understand this space, generating data from the development of activities and the relationship with nature.

The community, because it is there, has the power to build and transform new landscapes, new spaces, as well as their mental images, revealing more or less clear perceptual plans, according to their vital needs or limitations, according to their social and cultural priorities.

Perception inevitably influences human behaviour, but to maintain a quality environment, behaviour needs to be directed toward specific acts.

In addition, specific acts need to take precedence over other possible actions that reflect a different hierarchy of values.

Personal habits reflect an individual's value priorities, and considerate treatment of the environment requires an emphasis on environmental values.

Public information and education are indispensable, especially to develop the attitude known as environmental ethics.

Priorities within society have to be set for setting environmental goals. ”

It is possible to raise public participation by passing through the following three stages:

- a) raising awareness,
- b) Creating attitudes that influence actions and;
- c) Gain cooperation in problem solving.

To do so, one must initially diagnose the real state of public opinion and its trends.

Attitude research can provide an understanding of certain aspects, and interviews with public opinion leaders can develop an understanding of the motivations and dimensions of attitudes.

Awakening awareness is to inform the public about the relevance of a phenomenon to their lives. Inform in order to educate. Active participation is gained by offering an opportunity to express interest in real issues, especially when the theme indicates that participation can indeed influence an outcome.

Efficient decision making on environmental issues requires understanding how people perceive and evaluate the probabilities of uncertain events.

If it is the human being who makes decisions, his behaviour must be considered as a function of his real-world images and as a broad system in the information process, which is determined by the interaction of the individual's value systems and his real-world images.

The realization of social mobilization risks that the mutual influence of the psychological, economic and environmental factors activated by the public administration's attempt to control nature and the drafting of legislation, in the direction of decision making, thus compromising the efficiency of the plans. According to UNCED - United Nations Conference on Environment and Development, the best way to address environmental issues is with the participation of all concerned citizens.

And Environmental Education proves to be long term - as the best way to create critical awareness in the community, from the analysis of the problems experienced by it, and from this, effectively establish their participation in solving these same problems. .

Education, in turn, is a reading of nature. At the same time, the relationship with nature implies a certain relationship between individuals in society. As much as we are still in the early days of thinking about when, how, where and why of the environmental education methodology, everything leads us to believe in its success.

Environmental Education and Awareness Training (Awareness?)

Environmental education enters as an awareness tool. Created to act within national curricula in accordance with NCPs, (1998). Its history can be briefly described by the following steps:

1968 - The Club of Rome is founded which brings together scientists, economists and senior government officials from various countries to analyze the world situation and present predictions and solutions for the future (from an ecological perspective - global system).

The studies and proposals of this informal association, sponsored by the Volkswagen Foundation, inaugurated what was called ecomalthusianism. The first report of this organization was published in 1972 under the title: "The Limits of Growth."

They pointed to some factors that could lead to an unprecedented global crisis: Natural Resource Depletion, Energy Crisis, Population Growth, Food Shortage, Mass Unemployment, Environmental Pollution (the industrialization of the modern world is rapidly destroying the environment with backlash effects). and above any forecast).

1972 -The United Nations Conference in Stockholm took place under the theoretical aegis of thought emanating from the Club of Rome. It politicized the ecological theme and opened a new field in international relations: ecodiplomacy.

When the United Nations (UN) was created in 1945, they highlighted as priorities peace, human rights and equitable development, not being a priority or concern, in their early years the environmental issue and much less the ecological welfare.

Only after the Stockholm Conference on Human Environment in 1972 did ecological security become the United Nations' fourth priority.

1987 -The World Commission on Environment and Development (CMMAD), known as the Brundland Commission, recommended the creation of a universal charter or declaration on environmental protection and sustainable development. "Meet the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet

theirs as well." Our Common Future, Brundland Commission Report that inspired Rio-92.

1992 -United Nations Conference on Environment and Development (CNUMAD), held in Rio de Janeiro, also known as Rio-92 or ECO-92, twenty years after the Stockholm Conference, still felt the impact of the Club of Rome theories mainly in the form of approaches and proposals put forward by developed countries.

But in the interval between the two conferences, important transformations occurred in societies as well as in ecological and environmental thinking. Rio-92 was also the scene of criticism of the Club of Rome theories.

Eco 92 started the process and reached a first consensus on the "Rio Declaration of Principles" to continue the Earth Charter project. On this occasion, Agenda 21 was also made official as an international document of today's problems, preparing the world for the challenges of the 21st century.

1995 -International Earth Charter Seminar held in The Hague, The Netherlands. There the needs, the main elements and the way of elaboration of the Earth Charter were defined.

1996 - Climate Change Conference held in Kyoto, Japan and known as Rio + 5 for being held five years after the Echo 92. The official document of the Conference was known as the Kyoto Protocol, and was approved on 11.12.97, seeking the commitment to reduce about 6% of greenhouse gas emissions in industrialized countries by the period 2008 to 2012.

1997 -During Rio + 5 an Earth Charter Commission was formed. On that occasion came the text of the first draft of reference, which today marks the discussions around the world. The Earth Charter or Rio Declaration seeks to establish internationals that respect the interests of all and protect the integrity of the global ecology and development system.

It is understood that environmental education is essential for the formation of the individual as a citizen. Thus it is a legal instrument for the citizen to be environmentally aware, hence it can be charged through society as an obligation and political responsibility for its institutionalization. It should be dealt with as a transversal theme, according to the Curriculum Parameters and National Guidelines, as the Law prioritizes the Environmental Education projects in the elementary school subjects.

Research

Research is the daily attitude of the teacher and the student, where it is the subject of the process itself and systematize of the knowledge obtained.

Learning, through research, is a result of the processes used during its realization in obtaining knowledge.

Conducting a scientific research using a methodology becomes ideal for understanding the process itself and allows the systematic debate with reality to screen the paths that lead to the intended answers.

In exploratory studies the sources of information are the places or situations in which data are extracted that is needed, which is classified into three groups: field, laboratory and bibliography.

Field data collection provides the necessary data in the analysis.

In this data collection, the procedures are: bibliographic research from existing materials on the subject, in books, magazines, websites and case studies; interviews and research forms to foster problem data not yet evident. The research follows as qualitative research, using the data collected for analysis and comparison. Compare, describe, explain and juxtapose, without isolated, split and watertight views, constantly feeding and reformulating, where the collection can become analysis .

The research to be developed, from the point of view of its nature, is classified as applied research, with the objective of generating knowledge for practical application aimed at solving specific problems, involving local truths and interests.

Therefore, it will help environmental educators in the clarifications that permeate the impression given by the individual conscience facing the attitudes really exerted by such people, so that the barriers that limit the proposal of sustainability desired by humanity can be overcome.

Objective exploratory research, in general, seeks to clarify a situation for awareness.

The predominant approach is qualitative, with the collection and analysis of information. The qualitative aspect, may be present in information collected by essentially quantitative studies, but without losing its qualitative character when transformed into quantifiable data. Therefore, at times the quantitative approach elements will be used to define analysis indicators.

It is also considered descriptive as it achieves and exposes data representative of a given situation or phenomenon. The research, in this case, describes the perceptions of people who are considered to have environmental awareness.

References

- Abelson, P.H. (1977). "Energy and Climate." *Science* 197: 941.
- Annan, James D., and Julia C. Hargreaves (2006). "Using Multiple Observationally-Based Constraints to Estimate Climate Sensitivity." *Geophysical Research Letters* 33: L06704 [doi:10.1029/2005GL025259].
- Bauer, Eva, et al. (2003). "Assessing Climate Forcings of the Earth System for the Past Millennium." *Geophysical Research Letters* 30: 1276-80 [doi:10.1029/2002GL016639].
- Beuermann, Christiane, and Jill Jäger (1996). "Climate Change Politics in Germany." In *Politics of Climate Change: A European Perspective*, edited by Tim O'Riordan and Jill Jäger, pp. 186-227. London: Routledge.
- Bjørn Lomborg - *Prioritizing Development: A Cost Benefit Analysis of the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals* - Cambridge University Press, 2018
- Bjørn Lomborg - *How Much Have Global Problems Cost the World?* Cambridge University Press, 2013
- Bjørn Lomborg - *Global Problems, Smart Solutions - Costs and Benefits* - Cambridge University Press, 2013
- Bjørn Lomborg - *Smart Solutions to Climate Change* Cambridge University Press, 2010
- Bjørn Lomborg - *The Skeptical Environmentalist* Cambridge University Press, 2001
- Bolin, Bert (2007). *A History of the Science and Politics of Climate Change. The Role of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change.* Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Choat, Brendan, et al. (2012). "Global Convergence in the Vulnerability of Forests to Drought." *Nature* 491: 752-55 [doi:10.1038/nature11688].
- Clark, Peter U., et al. (2016). "Consequences of Twenty-First-Century Policy for Multi-Millennial Climate and Sea-Level Change." *Nature Climate Change* 6, 360-69 [doi:10.1038/nclimate2923].
- David, E.E., Jr. (1984). "Inventing the Future: Energy and the CO₂ 'Greenhouse' Effect." In *Climate Processes and Climate Sensitivity. (Geophysical Monograph 29, Maurice Ewing Vol. 5)*, edited by James E. Hansen and Taro Takahashi, pp. 1-5. Washington, DC: American Geophysical Union.
- Doran, P.T., and M. Kendall Zimmerman (2009). "Examining the Scientific Consensus on Climate Change." *Eos, Transactions of the American Geophysical Union* 90: 22-23 [doi:10.1029/2009EO030002].

Ehrlich, Paul R., and Anne H. Ehrlich (1970). *Population, Resources, Environment: Issues in Human Ecology*. San Francisco: Freeman.

Forster, Piers (2017). "In Retrospect: Half a Century of Robust Climate Models." *Nature* 545: 296-97 [doi:10.1038/545296a].

Gore, Albert, Jr. (1992). *Earth in the Balance: Ecology and the Human Spirit*. Boston: Houghton Mifflin.

Gore, Al (2006). *An Inconvenient Truth*. New York: Rodale Press

Jones, P. D., et al. (2008). "Urbanization Effects in Large-Scale Temperature Records, with an Emphasis on China." *Journal of Geophysical Research* 113: D16122 [doi:10.1029/2008JD009916].

Kasting, J.F., and T.P. Ackerman (1986). "Climate Consequences of Very High Carbon Dioxide Levels in the Earth's Early Atmosphere." *Science* 234: 1383-85.

Kates, R. W., et al., eds. (1985) *Climate Impact Assessment: Studies of the Interaction of Climate and Society*. SCOPE Publication 27. London: Wiley.

Lamb, Hubert H. (1972-77). *Climate: Present, Past and Future*. London: Methuen.

Lamb, Hubert H. (1977). *Climatic History and the Future*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press.

Lamb, Hubert H. (1995, 2nd ed.). *Climate, History and the Modern World*. London: Routledge.

Lamb, Hubert H. (1997). *Through All the Changing Scenes of Life: A Meteorologist's Tale*. Norfolk, UK: Taverner.

Lamb, Peter J. (2002). "The Climate Revolution: A Perspective." *Climatic Change* 54: 1-9 [https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1015778819992].

McNeill, J.R. (2000). *Something New under the Sun: An Environmental History of the Twentieth-Century World*. New York: W.W. Norton.

Sachs, Wolfgang, and Tilman Santarius, eds. *Fair Future: Resource Conflicts, Security, and Global Justice*. London: Zed Books, 2007.

W Sachs - *Development, Climate change and human rights* 2008 – Springer

W Sachs - *Global ecology Atlantic Highlands: Zed, 1993* - anchecata.colmich.edu.mx

W Sachs - *Fair future Industrial Ecology, 2008* – Springer

W Sachs - *Environment Development and human rights* , 2004 – Springer

Education and the Problem of "The Future" P Buckland - The International Journal of Illich Studies, 2013 - journals.psu.edu

Fritjof Capra Ugo Mattei The Ecology of Law: Toward a Legal System in Tune with Nature and Community Berrett-Koehler Publishers 2015

Ernest Callenbach Ecology, Revised and Expanded 1993